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Design and evaluation of Fe-Ni nanostructured catalysts via magnetron sputtering for CO₂-free hydrogen production

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ABSTRACT

Methane pyrolysis offers a promising route for CO₂-free hydrogen production. This study introduces a novel Fe-Ni catalyst architecture, synthesized via magnetron sputtering on γ -Al₂O₃ supports, designed to enhance methane decomposition efficiency. The process enabled the formation of Fe films (200–750 nm thick) with uniformly dispersed Ni nanoclusters (~2–3 at. %) on the surface. SEM, XRD, and XPS analyses confirmed the controlled nanostructure. Catalytic activity was evaluated at 800 °C using thermogravimetric analysis and a custom-built reactor. Results showed that Fe-Ni catalysts significantly increased hydrogen yield and carbon deposition. Gas analysis revealed elevated H₂ concentrations and minimal CO₂ presence (~0.1–0.2%), highlighting efficient catalytic performance and low carbon emissions. SEM revealed the growth of carbon nanotube-like structures, suggesting a vapor–liquid–solid growth mechanism. These findings contribute to the development of scalable and eco-friendly catalyst systems for decarbonizing hydrogen production.

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Introduction

Methane (CH₄), primarily sourced from natural gas and biomethane, is a crucial global energy resource due to its abundance and versatility in electricity generation and industrial applications. Over the past eight years, Europe's e-methane production capacity has surged from 20 GWh to 449 GWh per year, with projections indicating further increase to nearly 3,000 GWh annually by 2027, equivalent to 0.27 billion cubic

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meters (1). Globally by 2040, methane is expected to account for 28% of the primary energy mix, surpassing coal to become the second-largest energy source after oil (2). Beyond its energy applications, methane serves as key feedstock for hydrogen production. It is often referred to as a 'bridge fuel' due to its comparatively lower emissions than coal and oil, supporting climate goals under the Paris Agreement (3). However, conventional methane combustion still produces approximately 450 g of CO₂ per kWh, highlighting challenges to its sustainability as a long-term strategy for deep decarbonization (3, 4).

Given the limitations of conventional hydrogen production, hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a key component of the clean energy transition. It serves both as a flexible energy carrier and a critical industrial feedstock. However, current production methods pose significant environmental challenges. The predominant method, steam methane reforming (SMR), produces approximately 95% of global hydrogen but also emits substantial amounts of CO₂, averaging 9–12 kg CO₂ per kg of hydrogen produced (5). An alternative method, water electrolysis, produces hydrogen without direct emissions, yet requires 50–55 kWh of electricity per kg of hydrogen, limiting its efficiency and large-scale application due to high energy demands and limited availability of renewable electricity (6). In contrast, methane pyrolysis has emerged as a promising hydrogen production technology that effectively decouples hydrogen generation from CO₂ emissions. This process, represented by the chemical reaction $\text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{C} + 2\text{H}_2$, produces solid carbon instead of CO₂, making it a viable route for 'turquoise hydrogen' – a term used for hydrogen derived from methane pyrolysis. The energy requirement for methane pyrolysis is 37.5 kJ/mol H₂, which is lower than that of SMR (41.4 kJ/mol H₂ with water evaporation and 63.4 kJ/mol H₂ without it), and significantly lower than hydrogen production via electrolysis (285.9 kJ/mol H₂) (7, 8). This makes pyrolysis particularly advantageous for decarbonizing hard-to-electrify industries, such as steelmaking and cement production, where direct electrification is challenging (9–11). Additionally, when biomethane is used as the feedstock, methane pyrolysis can be carbon-neutral or even carbon-negative, with solid carbon by-product offering commercial value in industries such as construction and electronics (12). Compared to electrolysis, this process typically requires only 12–15 kWh per kg of hydrogen, making it significantly more energy-efficient (6).

To further explore this promising technology, three primary methods of methane pyrolysis are being indicated, each with distinct advantages and challenges: (i) Thermal Pyrolysis. This method operates at high temperatures (>1000 °C) to decompose methane into hydrogen and solid carbon. While it efficiently produces hydrogen, its high energy requirements present a significant challenge for large-scale deployment. Integrating renewable energy sources, such as concentrated solar power, could improve its sustainability by offsetting some of the energy demand (8, 12). (ii) Plasma Pyrolysis. This method employs ionized gases (plasma) to achieve the high temperatures required for methane decomposition, allowing for faster molecular dissociation than thermal methods. However, the high cost of plasma generation and equipment limits its industrial adoption (13). (iii) Catalyst-Based Pyrolysis. Operating at significantly lower temperatures (500–900 °C), it requires less energy and allows greater control over reaction conditions. Catalyst-based pyrolysis typically results in higher hydrogen yields and lower operational costs. Additionally, catalysts, such as nickel or carbon-based materials, enable the production of high-purity solid carbon by-products, including valuable forms like carbon nanotubes. This added commercial value, combined with lower energy demands, makes catalyst-based pyrolysis particularly promising for sustainable and economically viable hydrogen production (12, 14).

Catalysts are essential to the efficiency and feasibility of methane pyrolysis, by enabling decomposition at lower temperatures and reduction of overall energy consumption. By providing an alternative reaction pathway, catalysts improve the sustainability of this process. However, metal-based catalysts face challenges, particularly deactivation caused by carbon deposition over time. Continuous advancements in catalytic materials that improve stability, activity and selectivity are crucial for maximizing the potential of methane pyrolysis for hydrogen production. Current research aims to extend catalyst lifespan, reduce operational costs and expand industrial applications (15, 16). Although a variety of metal- or carbon-based catalysts are discussed in the literature, research is still lacking to meet all the requirements for an efficient catalytic structure (17). Among the commonly used metal catalysts, nickel (Ni), iron (Fe), cobalt (Co), and cost-ineffective noble metals (Pt, Pd, Au, and Ir) (18, 19) have demonstrated high catalytic activity and effectiveness in methane decomposition, with nickel being particularly valued for its cost-effectiveness and ability to promote high hydrogen yields (19–22). In terms of catalytic performance, Ni exhibits the highest activity, followed by Co and Fe. However, Co should be avoided as it is classified as a Critical Raw Material (CRM) in the European Union. Additionally, Ni tends to deactivate above 600°C due to surface encapsulation by solid

carbon by-products (23). Fe is slightly less active and works in higher temperatures (700–1000 °C) than Ni, but is much more resistant to deactivation (18, 24, 25).

To improve catalytic durability and performance, bimetallic catalysts have been investigated as an alternative approach (26). The development of a bimetallic catalyst (e.g. doping Fe with Ni (27)) is one of the promising ways to prolong the lifetime and increase the stability of the catalyst. For instance, several studies have shown that Fe-Ni catalysts can improve catalytic performance by enhancing stability and resistance to carbon deposition (28–30). C. Ellison et al. synthesized activated carbon-supported Ni, Fe, and NiFe catalysts via wet impregnation for CO_x-free hydrogen production through microwave methane pyrolysis. They observed that nickel supported on activated carbon (Ni/AC) achieved the highest H₂ yield (46.9%) at 800 °C, yet suffered from rapid deactivation due to carbon deposition. In contrast, the bimetallic NiFe/AC catalyst exhibited slightly lower activity (H₂ yield: 40.5%) but demonstrated better resistance to carbon formation (28). S. A. Theofanidis et al. investigated Fe-Ni/MgAl₂O₄ catalysts for methane dry reforming, examining Fe's role in enhancing carbon resistance. They found that Fe-Ni alloy formation improves catalyst stability (30). However, improvements are still needed to achieve better catalytic performance.

The synergy between iron and nickel optimizes catalytic performance, as evidenced by the high activity levels reported in similar iron-nickel systems (31, 32). It also generates high-purity solid carbon while effectively reducing CO₂ emissions in comparison to traditional methods (33). By optimizing the synergy between iron and nickel, this catalyst presents an efficient and scalable solution for methane pyrolysis (34–36).

The synthesis process also determines the properties of the catalyst. Various chemical synthesis methods, including co-precipitation (37–39), sol-gel processes (40, 41), and hydrothermal synthesis (39, 42, 43), have been used to create bimetallic catalysts. These methods have demonstrated improved hydrogen yields and reduced deactivation rates compared to monometallic counterparts (44, 45). However, chemical synthesis methods are often complex, time-consuming, and temperature-dependent, while also generating undesirable reaction by-products. Therefore, the catalyst stability and performance remain crucial to the commercial viability of methane pyrolysis. Exploring alternative synthesis methods that can achieve even more uniform and durable coatings is essential. Magnetron sputtering is a prominent method, which enables the deposition of highly uniform coatings, enhancing material properties and contributing to longer-lasting catalytic performance. Magnetron sputtering has many advantages over traditional synthesis methods, including easy deposition of nearly all metals, alloys and compounds, high deposited film purity, and strong adhesion with the substrate.

In this study, we investigate the synthesis of Fe-based catalysts with Ni nanoclusters supported on γ -Al₂O₃ using magnetron sputtering and evaluate their performance in catalyst-based methane pyrolysis.

The choice of γ -Al₂O₃ as a catalyst support is deliberate due to its widespread industrial use, excellent physicochemical properties, including high surface area, thermal stability, and strong metal-support interaction (46). These characteristics not only facilitate the dispersion of active metal particles but also help minimize deactivation under high-temperature conditions typical for methane pyrolysis (12). Additionally, porous structure of γ -Al₂O₃ promotes gas diffusion and access to active sites, which is essential for achieving efficient methane decomposition. Previous studies (47–49) have confirmed its successful use in supporting Ni-, Fe-, and bimetallic catalysts for CO_x-free hydrogen production, further validating its suitability for this application. γ -Al₂O₃-supported catalysts is a highly suitable support for Fe/Ni-based systems used in methane decomposition.

Unlike conventional catalyst synthesis methods, magnetron sputtering offers precise control over catalyst composition and structure, potentially enhancing performance and stability. While iron catalysts typically undergo reduction with CO_x emissions (50). This study explores an eco-friendly, one-step fabrication method that minimizes such emissions. To the best of our knowledge, Fe-Ni nanocluster catalysts have not yet been studied for methane pyrolysis. This work aims to fill this gap and contribute to the development of more efficient, scalable, and sustainable hydrogen production technologies.

Materials and methods

Catalyst synthesis procedure

To prepare the Fe-Ni catalyst supported on γ -Al₂O₃, a combination of gamma alumina chemical synthesis and magnetron sputtering deposition was employed. The catalyst support, γ -Al₂O₃, was synthesized following

Figure 1. The principal scheme of the magnetron sputtering system for catalyst deposition on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support.

the procedure described in our previous patent (EP3768640B1) and article (51). A laboratory oven (SNOL 7.2/900 LSC01) was used for both the synthesis and annealing of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

A magnetron physical vapor deposition (PVD) system (Figure 1) was used to synthesize an iron catalyst enhanced with nickel nanoclusters on a $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support. Inside the vacuum system, two circular magnetrons equipped with Fe (99.99%) and Ni (99.99%) targets were installed and powered by a DC power source (Iron: $I_{\text{Fe}} = 0.8$ A, $U_{\text{Fe}} = 480 \pm 20$ V; Nickel: $I_{\text{Ni}} = 0.5$ A, $U_{\text{Ni}} = 450 \pm 20$ V). Below them, a rotating substrate holder was mounted, holding a Petri dish with $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder. The distance between the magnetron and the samples was 5 cm. Initially, the chamber was evacuated using rotary and diffusion pumps until a base pressure of 4×10^{-3} mbar was reached. Then argon gas was introduced as the working gas, maintaining a deposition pressure of 6×10^{-2} mbar. The Fe deposition time varied between 1 and 5 min, depending on the desired metal loading, whereas Ni deposition was limited to 50 s to promote nanocluster formation rather than continuous film growth.

The catalyst formation involved multiple stages: (a) Initial deposition of Fe onto $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder; (b) The $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder was extracted, manually mixed, and returned for a second Fe deposition to enhance reproducibility and uniformity; (c) The Fe-coated $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder was repositioned under the Ni target for Ni nanocluster deposition; (d) To ensure an even distribution of Ni nanoclusters, the powder was removed, mixed, and subjected to a second Ni nanocluster deposition step.

Characterization

The morphology of the catalyst surface, including surface texture, was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-3400N). Elemental composition analysis was conducted via energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, Bruker Quad 5040) for qualitative assessment of elemental distribution. The coating thickness was measured using a Bruker DektakXT stylus profilometer. The crystal structure of the catalyst was analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a Bruker D8 diffractometer, operating at 40 kV and 40 mA in the θ - θ configuration. The key measurement parameters included Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm), a scan range of 20–70°, and a 0.3° fixed divergence slit. The obtained XRD patterns were analyzed using the PDF-5 + database (ICDD) as a reference. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, PHI 5000 Versaprobe) was employed to determine the surface elemental composition and chemical states of elements. Quantitative analysis of the XPS spectra was performed using Multipak software. The spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 187.85 eV, using monochromated Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV, 25 W beam power), a 100 μm beam size, and a 45° measurement angle.

Methane pyrolysis and gas analysis

To investigate preliminary hydrogen production and the influence of temperature, experiments were conducted using thermogravimetric analysis (Labsys Evo TGA) setup, connected in-line with mass spectrometry

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the reactor.

(Shimadzu, Nexis GC-2030). This setup was used to monitor mass changes upon methane introduction and to evaluate the pyrolysis process. The cell was evacuated to pressure of at least 10^{-1} mbar, then heated to 800 °C. Methane was introduced at a flow rate of $100 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Mass changes due to carbon deposition in tandem with the gas composition were recorded and analyzed as a function of heating time.

To evaluate the precise gas composition at a larger scale, the pyrolysis reaction was carried out in an in-house-built reactor, schematically depicted in Figure 2. The sample was loaded into the reactor, and air was evacuated using a fore vacuum pump. Methane was then introduced into the system. The heating protocol was set to reach a target temperature of 800 °C over 120 min. Once the target temperature was reached, the reaction was maintained for 1–3 h. After the heating phase, the system was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature. Following pyrolysis, gas samples were collected using a Restek gas sampling bottle and analyzed with a mass spectrometer (RGA100 MS, Stanford Research Systems). Post-reaction, the solid samples were analyzed via SEM and XRD to examine changes in crystalline structure and carbon morphology.

Results and discussion

Fe film and Ni nanoclusters formation on a flat surface

Before synthesizing Fe catalysts with Ni nanoclusters on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, it was necessary to determine and optimize the most favorable magnetron sputtering parameters. To achieve this, a series of preliminary experiments were conducted, varying the target-to-substrate distance, gas regimes, and sputtering power. These experiments were crucial for understanding the characteristics of the deposited structures and confirming the successful formation of Fe films with embedded Ni nanoclusters. Initial depositions were carried out on flat quartz substrates to evaluate structural properties and refine growth conditions. The primary objective was to create a solid Fe film to serve as the main catalytic material for methane pyrolysis, while the Ni nanoclusters were intended to enhance the pyrolysis process by lowering the activation temperature compared to pure Fe.

During deposition rate experiments, it was observed that under a discharge voltage of 450 V, current of 0.5 A, and a target-to-substrate distance of 5 cm resulted in an average deposition rate of 3 nm per second. Based on these findings, the deposition parameters were fixed, and the film deposition time was varied to investigate the effect of film thickness on methane pyrolysis performance. As a result, deposition times of 1, 3, and 5 min were selected for the formation of the Fe film. Figure 3 presents the XRD pattern of a Fe film

Figure 3. XRD pattern of Fe deposited by magnetron sputtering on a quartz substrate.

(JCPDS: 00-006-0696) deposited onto a quartz substrate for 3 min. The diffraction peaks indicate that the coating is completely crystallized, confirming the formation of a well-defined Fe structure under the given deposition conditions.

To form Ni nanoclusters on the Fe film, it was hypothesized that during the early stages of magnetron sputtering, the deposited material initially forms discrete islands. These islands eventually coalesce into a continuous film as deposition progresses. Therefore, to achieve nanocluster formation, the deposition process was carefully limited to the island growth regime, before a continuous Ni layer could develop (Figure 4a).

Figure 4 illustrates the elemental analysis of the deposited film on quartz substrate for all detected chemical elements (b), iron (c), and nickel (d). The elemental mapping reveals that iron is evenly distributed across the entire coating surface, whereas nickel is present not as a uniform coating but rather as localized structures.

To further evaluate the chemical state and distribution of Fe and Ni, XPS measurements were performed. XPS analysis is particularly advantageous in this context due to its measurement depth of approximately 10

Figure 4. Schematic of the formation (a) and elemental mapping (b, c, d) of Fe film with Ni nanoclusters deposited on a quartz substrate.

Figure 5. XPS survey spectra of Fe film with Ni nanoclusters deposited on a quartz substrate.

nm, allowing for precise surface characterization. If Ni were forming a continuous coating on the surface, the underlying iron would not be detectable using this method. However, the detection of iron via XPS confirms that nickel exists predominantly as discrete nanoclusters rather than a uniform layer. These findings validate the effectiveness of the deposition process in achieving the desired nanocluster architecture, providing a foundation for further catalytic studies.

Figure 5 illustrates the XPS survey spectrum of the Fe film formed with Ni nanoclusters. The analysis indicates that the surface layer contains carbon (C, 32.6 at. %), oxygen (O, 35.7 at. %), Fe (14.9 at. %), and Ni (16.9 at. %). The presence of carbon and oxygen is characteristic of surface structures, while the detection of both Fe and Ni confirms the coexistence of these elements on the surface. These results align with previous findings indicating that Fe forms a continuous coating, whereas Ni is distributed in the form of nanoclusters on the surface.

Based on these findings, subsequent experiments focused on catalyst formation on a γ - Al_2O_3 substrate. Fe films were deposited using three different sputtering durations – 1, 3, and 5 min – corresponding to approximate thicknesses of 200 nm (FeNi-1), 500 nm (FeNi-2), and 750 nm (FeNi-3), respectively. In all cases, the deposition time for Ni nanocluster formation was fixed at 50 s. Fe film thicknesses were estimated by performing profilometric analysis on samples deposited onto quartz substrates under the same conditions. Additionally, a pure Fe film was deposited on γ - Al_2O_3 powder for 3 min as a reference.

Fe film and Ni nanoclusters formation on a γ - Al_2O_3 powder

SEM and EDS analysis were performed to understand and compare the synthesized catalyst surface morphology and elemental mapping. Figure 6a illustrates the morphology of pure γ - Al_2O_3 powder, which exhibits a broad size distribution ranging from hundreds of nanometers to tens of microns and retains a highly porous structure. Following Fe-Ni deposition, the overall morphology remained largely unchanged (Figure 6b), indicating that the deposition process does not significantly alter the porous nature of γ - Al_2O_3 . Elemental mapping results confirm the successful deposition of Fe and Ni onto the γ - Al_2O_3 surface. Both elements adhere to the underlying substrate morphology, ensuring uniform surface coverage. Notably, while the distribution of Ni remains consistent across all samples, Fe intensity increases with longer deposition times, reinforcing the stability and reproducibility of the magnetron sputtering method for Fe-Ni catalyst synthesis.

Figure 6. SEM images and elemental mapping of catalyst deposited on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder (FeNi-1 sample): pure $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder (a), FeNi catalyst on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (b), elemental mapping – all elements (c), Fe and Ni (d), Fe (e), Ni (f), Al (g), and O (h).

Figure 7 shows the XRD patterns of the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ substrate, pure Fe, and Fe films with Ni nanoclusters deposited on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder. A detailed examination of the patterns reveals that the predominant crystal-line structure, represented by most of the observed peaks, corresponds to $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (marked with a 'star' sign JCPDS: 00-056-0457). According to the comparative analysis presented in Figure 2, the expected diffraction peaks for Fe are positioned at approximately 45° and 65° (2θ). However, the detection of distinct Fe-related peaks was hindered by significant overlap with the intense $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ signals. A more pronounced and distinguishable Fe structure was detected exclusively in the FeNi-3 sample, having the highest amount of deposited Fe. The pronounced intensity of the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ peaks effectively masks the diffraction signals from both Fe and Ni, limiting the effectiveness of XRD in identifying these phases. To address this limitation and achieve a more comprehensive characterization, XPS was employed for further investigation.

The results of the survey spectra and the corresponding elemental concentrations are presented in Figure 8 and Table 1, respectively. The analysis reveals the presence of O, C, Al, Fe, and Ni chemical elements across all samples, with the exception of the 'Fe' sample, where the synthesis of Ni nanoclusters was deliberately excluded. The detected carbon is attributed to a naturally occurring layer of carbonaceous compounds on the material surfaces. This layer forms as a result of surface interactions, leading to the presence of functional groups such as C–O, C=O, as well as other carbon-containing compounds (52).

Figure 7. XRD patterns of the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ substrate and Fe films without and with Ni nanoclusters deposited on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder.

The observed aluminium (Al) content originates from the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ substrate, which serves as the base for the deposition of the catalytic materials. The data demonstrates a gradual decrease in the Al content of the surface as the iron deposition time increases. Specifically, the Al concentration decreases from 14.2 at. % in the FeNi-1 sample (1 min Fe deposition) to 11.4 at. % in the FeNi-3 sample (5 min deposition). This trend indicates the increasing coverage of the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ surface by the deposited Fe layer, effectively masking the substrate material. In contrast, the Fe content on the surface exhibits a clear upward trend with increasing deposition time. It rises from 5.2 at. % for the 1 min deposition to 6.8 at. % for the 5 min deposition time. This observation correlates with the progressive accumulation of Fe on the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ surface, demonstrating successful deposition of the Fe film over time. Meanwhile, the Ni content remains relatively stable across all

Figure 8. XPS survey spectra of Fe films with Ni nanoclusters deposited on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder.

Table 1. Top-layer elemental composition of Fe films with Ni nanoclusters deposited on γ - Al_2O_3 powder.

Sample	Atomic concentration, at. %				
	O	C	Al	Fe	Ni
Fe	59.0	10.8	24.1	6.1	–
FeNi-1	53.4	24.6	14.2	5.2	2.6
FeNi-2	54.7	23.7	13.5	5.9	2.1
FeNi-3	54.6	24.1	11.4	6.8	3.1

samples, varying only slightly within the range of 2–3 at. %. This consistency suggests a controlled and uniform deposition of Ni nanoclusters, independent of the varying Fe film thicknesses.

The chemical bond analysis was performed on the Fe2p (Figure 9a) and O1s (Figure 9b) spectra of Fe deposited on γ - Al_2O_3 powder to understand the oxidation state and local bonding environment of Fe. The Fe2p spectra were deconvoluted into four components, comprising Fe^{3+} at Fe2p_{3/2} (710.1 eV), its corresponding doublet at Fe2p_{1/2} (723.7 eV), along with their satellite peaks. These binding energies are characteristic of the Fe_2O_3 phase, consistent with the expected oxidation state of Fe^{3+} in the deposited material. Notably, no metallic Fe phase was detected in the spectrum, indicating that the entire deposited Fe structure underwent oxidation during or after the deposition process. This result confirms the complete conversion of Fe into Fe_2O_3 , with no residual metallic phase present in the sample surface.

This interpretation was further supported by the O1s spectrum, which revealed two distinct components. The first component, at 529.3 eV, corresponds to oxygen bound in Fe_2O_3 , confirming the oxidized nature of the deposited Fe. The second component, at 531.3 eV, was attributed to oxygen in the substrate material, γ - Al_2O_3 , consistent with the expected chemical environment of the alumina support.

While the XRD results confirm the metallic Fe state, the XPS findings suggest that only the top layer of deposited Fe was oxidized during the synthesis or after the catalyst extraction to the atmosphere. The results obtained from those two methods complement each other, while XRD typically probes the crystalline structure of materials to depths of several micrometres, whereas XPS is a surface-sensitive technique that analyses only the top 1–10 nanometers of a sample. Fe_2O_3 demonstrates strong catalytic stability under methane pyrolysis conditions. However, it is generally less efficient than metallic Fe in terms of methane conversion rates and hydrogen yield. Pure metallic Fe exhibits higher catalytic activity due to its ability to adsorb and dissociate methane molecules more effectively (49). Despite Fe_2O_3 having lower activity compared to metallic Fe, its enhanced thermal stability and resistance to fouling make it an attractive option for applications where prolonged catalytic operation is required. Thus, while pure Fe remains a better choice for maximizing methane conversion in short-duration processes, Fe_2O_3 serves as a robust precursor and support, particularly in systems designed for stable, long-term performance.

Methane pyrolysis

Figure 10 presents XRD results of samples after methane pyrolysis at 800 °C. Slight variations in peak positions are observed across samples, particularly in the 2θ range corresponding to carbon peaks at approximately 25.5° and 43.5°. Among the samples, FeNi-3 exhibits the highest intensity of carbon peak at 25.5°.

Figure 9. Fe2p (a) and O1s (b) spectra XPS fitting results of Fe deposited on γ - Al_2O_3 powder.

Figure 10. XRD of samples after pyrolysis at 800 °C (a) held for 1 h. The same peaks are visible as indicated in Figure 6, but additional carbon peaks are present. (b) held at times 1, 2, 4 h, peak position and form do not change with increased reaction time.

Other diffraction peaks remain largely consistent across samples in terms of position and relative intensity. With increasing reaction time, the carbon peak is also increasing, following an approximately linear trend in this region. Notably, a peak near 51° appears after pyrolysis. Lu et al. attributed a similar peak at 50.8° to $\text{Fe}_{0.64}\text{Ni}_{0.36}$ (#47-1405) (53). Dawkins et al. assigned the same peak to metallic Fe (54), while Wang et al. reported a strong peak at 51.8° in Ni-doped gamma alumina, as well as the presence of NiFe_3 (55). Considering the expected amount of Ni in our samples, it is unlikely that this peak corresponds to metallic Ni.

To investigate the carbon deposition and growth on the catalysts, TG analysis was performed in a methane environment. Prior to introduction of methane, the sample was heated in vacuum for a set duration. CH_4 was then introduced at a flow rate of 100 mL/min. The observed sharp mass change is attributed to mechanical switching artifacts inherent to TG device. This was followed by a rapid mass increase, as shown in Figure 11a. Simultaneously, gas composition was monitored using GC-MS. A summary of the composition is presented in Figure 11b. From TG, we see the highest mass increase of 35.56% for sample FeNi-3, then decreasing with decreasing amount of Fe deposited. From GC-MS, we see the presence of CO and hydrogen. It is noteworthy that in this flow setup, the reaction at these catalyst amounts does not show large efficiency, i.e. only a couple of percent. Thus, a reactor with a substantial CH_4 /catalyst ratio was used for further analysis.

Figure 12 presents the results of gas analysis, highlighting the influence of catalyst composition—particularly Fe content—and heating temperature on the reaction products. As shown in Figure 12a, the tandem

Figure 11. TG analysis of catalysts in methane flow. (a) mass change with heating in methane flow; (b) in-line GC-MS gas analysis.

Figure 12. Gas and carbon yield analysis of the pyrolysis reaction depending on the sample and reaction temperature. (a) general screening of CH₄ and H₂ content dependent on Fe deposition; (b) CO₂ content evaluation; (c) CO content evaluation; (d) Compound view of gas content dependence on reaction temperature.

catalyst (Fe with Ni nanoclusters) is more efficient in comparison to just Fe, as the yield of hydrogen is higher, which proves that the selected deposition method could be used for hydrogen production.

During the reaction, iron oxide in the catalyst is reduced to metallic Fe, which actively contributes to methane decomposition until deactivation occurs due to carbon deposition. As a result, some CO_x formation is expected and was confirmed by GC-MS analysis. CO and CO₂ content dependence on the reaction temperature is shown in Figures 12b and c, respectively. CO₂ was detected at all tested temperatures, though typically at very low levels (~0.1–0.2%), which are near the specified detection threshold of the instrument. It is possible to calculate exact content by utilizing the consistent peak ratios and individually calculating the composition of each peak. However, in this experimental series, it is assumed that 0.2% is the selected limit, below which the CO₂ content is assumed to be negligible. At the same time, the CO content is the lowest for FeNi-2, moderate for FeNi-3 and higher for FeNi-1, as seen in Figure 12c, indicating varying degrees of Fe dispersion. This presumably supports the reduction of Fe₂O₃ to metallic Fe and corresponds to the XRD results (Figure 10).

Figure 12d shows the relationship between reaction temperature, residual CH₄, and hydrogen production. As the temperature increases, CH₄ concentration decreases while hydrogen yield generally increases. An exception is observed for the FeNi-2 sample, where hydrogen production at 800 °C is lower than at 700 °C. This suggests that the selected catalyst deposition method reduces the temperature required for effective methane decomposition, but further optimization is needed.

If we compare the activity window for these catalysts with the literature data, noticeable variations emerge. For instance, Wang et al. (55) investigated Fe/Al₂O₃ catalysts with Fe loadings ranging from 10% to 60%, synthesized via the dry impregnation method. Their XPS analysis revealed a strong interaction

Table 2. Comparison of catalytic performance for methane pyrolysis using Fe-, Ni-, and FeNi-based catalysts reported in literature.

Catalyst	Support	Method	Temperature, °C	H ₂ yield, %	Reference
Ni	CeO ₂	Facile solid state citrate fusion	700	53	(56)
Fe	CeO ₂	Co-precipitation	700	51	(57)
80%Fe	Al ₂ O ₃	Co-precipitation	700	75	(58)
Ni	TiO ₂	Sol-gel	700	56	(59)
Ni	Al ₂ O ₃	Co-precipitation	700	50	(60)
Ni-Fe	MgO-Al ₂ O ₃	Sol-gel	600	56	(61)
Ni-Fe	Mesoporous silica	Facile wet impregnation route	700	34	(62)
Fe	SiO ₂	Facile wet impregnation route	800	39	(63)
Fe with Ni nanoclusters	Laboratory-made γ -Al ₂ O ₃	Magnetron sputtering	800	50	This work

between Fe and the oxygen species of Al₂O₃, which inhibited Fe agglomeration. At 700 °C, they reported hydrogen yields of 18% for the lowest Fe loading and up to 58% for the highest, with a peak activity window of approximately 15 min, after which catalyst deactivation occurred across all loadings.

If we consider just Ni catalyst on Al₂O₃ as investigated by Wang et al. with other co-catalysts, the reported H₂ yield reaches 50% with Ni alone, where the addition of Fe brings the conversion rate to around 53%. In all cases, samples started to deactivate. It is noteworthy that in this case reaction temperature was 650 °C (55). As aforementioned, Al-Fatesh et al. investigated FeCo catalysts compared to pure Fe oxides, with very low activity, under 15% for pure Fe and up to 53% with mixed catalysts, maintaining activity for over 400 min (54).

To evaluate the performance of the synthesized catalyst, Table 2 presents a comparative summary of methane pyrolysis catalysts reported in the literature. The comparison includes different metal compositions, supports, synthesis methods, and reaction conditions. It highlights that the catalyst presented in this work achieves a competitive hydrogen yield under comparable conditions. It should be noted that for rigorous comparison of catalytic performance, experiments must be conducted under identical conditions and within the same reactor system. Variations in experimental setups, such as reactor geometry, gas flow rates, and catalyst loading, can influence the observed activity, making direct comparisons across studies inherently qualitative.

SEM analysis revealed the presence of various carbon structures, as shown in the micrograph of the sample before pyrolysis (Figure 13a). Following the reaction at 800 °C, significant carbon growth was observed, as illustrated in Figure 13b. Notably, carbon deposition does not occur uniformly across the surface but appears concentrated at specific sites. The γ -Al₂O₃ support remained largely free of carbon, indicating that carbon growth predominantly occurs on the Fe and Ni catalytic sites. A closer examination in Figure 13c shows that carbon structures – such as strands or tubes – emerged from metallic catalyst particles, many of which are located at the tips of the carbon formations. This morphology supports the vapor-liquid-solid (VLS) growth mechanism, as described by Prabowo et al (64). As can be seen in Figure 13c, single-wall nanotubes can be created in this reaction. On the other hand, there is a substantial amount of other tubular and semi-tubular structures visible, similar to defined variations by Zhang et al., including nano onions as a base of further tubular structures (65). As illustrated in Figure 13d, the relationship between carbon yield and temperature is not linear, particularly for the FeNi-1 and FeNi-2 samples. This suggests a more complex interplay between catalyst loading, temperature, and carbon morphology.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the successful design, fabrication, and evaluation of Fe-Ni nanostructured catalysts synthesized via magnetron sputtering on γ -Al₂O₃ supports for methane pyrolysis and CO₂-free hydrogen production. The precise control offered by magnetron sputtering enabled the formation of well-defined Fe films (200–750 nm) and uniformly distributed Ni nanoclusters (2–3 at. %) as confirmed by SEM, XRD, and XPS analysis. The catalytic performance of these structures was tested at 800 °C in both thermogravimetric and custom-built reactor setups.

Variations in Fe content substantially influenced hydrogen yield, while the presence of Ni nanoclusters enhanced catalytic efficiency for turquoise hydrogen production. Among all samples, the FeNi-3 catalyst

Figure 13. SEM micrographs of the catalyst after the pyrolysis reaction. (a) catalyst after pyrolysis reaction at 2 kx magnification; (b) closer look at the catalyst after pyrolysis at 20 kx magnification; (c) 100 kx magnification of carbon deposited; (d) evaluated carbon deposition yield after pyrolysis.

delivered the highest hydrogen yield (~50%) and a carbon mass gain of 35.56% at 800 °C, indicating efficient methane decomposition. At 900 °C, all samples exhibited hydrogen yields exceeding 65%; however, this temperature also may lead to increased catalyst degradation and energy consumption. Carbon morphology analysis revealed nanotube-like structures indicative of a vapor–liquid–solid growth mechanism. Furthermore, gas analysis confirmed high H₂ selectivity and low CO₂ emissions (~0.1–0.2%), underscoring the environmental benefits of this synthesis method. But further elaboration and analysis of the CO₂ content should be carried out.

Compared to conventional catalyst fabrication techniques, magnetron sputtering offers a scalable, low-waste, and highly tuneable method, enhancing both catalytic activity and thermal stability. These findings establish Fe–Ni catalysts prepared via magnetron sputtering as a promising route for sustainable and industrially scalable turquoise hydrogen production. However, comprehensive experimental investigations are required to assess catalyst reusability and long-term performance.

Future research should prioritize optimizing the Fe–Ni composition, enhancing catalyst durability, and scaling up the synthesis process. Regarding catalyst reuse, a key challenge lies in the accumulation of coked carbon following methane pyrolysis, which significantly impairs catalytic activity. Therefore, innovative regeneration strategies need to be explored in the future’s scientific works to restore catalyst performance and ensure the overall sustainability of the process.

Author contributions

CRedit: **Marius Urbonavicius:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Sarunas Varnagiris:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Simona Tuckute:** Investigation, Project administration, Writing – original draft; **Darius Milcius:** Investigation; **Ainars Knoks:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review &

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Marius Urbonavicius, upon reasonable request.

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